

The presence of gastrointestinal symptoms in a family case report of SARS-CoV-2 and how the timing of drugs administration can determine a different disease behavior.

Author: Brogna Carlo, M.D.

Affiliation:

Carlo Brogna - Craniomed group srl, Montemiletto, Italy - email dir.brogna@craniomed.it

Abstract.

The home health care of COVID-19 patients is a very big challenge. The different therapeutic choices given by non-hospital doctors are often different and without a unique guideline. In this study, we constated the COVID-19 therapy with or without Hydroxychloroquine and with azithromycin in a family group given by the same doctor. Four family people were affected by SARS-CoV-2. They are divided into two small groups. The adult group hired Hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin and the child group only azithromycin. The outcome obtained were different. A male adult coming out is slower than the three female family people. This family case report collects the decisive choices in disease treatment and management. The results suggest a particular observation on child therapy and coming out.

Keywords: COVID-19; TMPRSS2; phospholipase A2; ACE2; Chloroquine; hydroxychloroquine; SARS-CoV-2; azithromycin; antibiotics.

Introduction.

In December 2019, the world was infected with the SARS-CoV-2 virus. At April 2020 end, almost 180,000 deaths worldwide[1]. In Wuhan, 73% of patients infected (average age 49 years) were men, 32% were with some medical condition: diabetes (20%), hypertension (15%) cardiovascular disease (15%). The most common

symptoms onset were fever (98%), cough (76%), and myalgia or fatigue (44%). Other few symptoms: sputum (28%), headaches, hemoptysis, diarrhea[2]. In a study, Zhou F. et al. described that the average time from the first symptom to breathlessness was 5 days, to the hospitalization 7 days and ARDS 8 days[3]. Lymphopenia was present in 63%. Guan WJ et al.[2] said that many people had interstitial pneumonia. Acute respiratory distress syndrome (29%), RNA growth (15%), acute heart damage (12%), secondary infection (10%) were the complications. Wang described that most patients received antiviral therapy (oseltamivir, 89.9%) and many received antibacterial therapy (moxifloxacin, 64.4%; ceftriaxone, 24.6%; azithromycin, 18.1% and glucocorticoid therapy, 44.9%)[4]. Between 26.1% and 32% of patients needed intensive care due to complications, including acute respiratory distress syndrome (61.1%), arrhythmia (44.4%) shock (30.6%)[4]. Zang observed the latter had higher plasma levels of IL2, IL7, IL10, GSCF, IP10, MCP1, MIP1A, and TNF[5]. Patients treated in intensive care, compared to patients not treated in intensive care, were older (median age, 66 years vs. 51 years), and 72.2% had underlying comorbidity[4], [6]. The attention to the digestive system was first reported by a Chinese group[7]. The gastrointestinal tract and liver are also the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) target organs. Angiotensin conversion enzyme 2 (ACE2), the SARS-CoV-2 main receptor, is expressed both in the gastrointestinal tract and in liver cells[8]. The viral RNA is present in the patients' feces and the oral-fecal transmission worries and represents a huge obstacle [9]–[11]. A link between gastrointestinal involvement and the COVID-19 severity disease has been suggested. In a multicenter study, Pan and colleagues[12] studied this aspect. They described 99 patients who had digestive symptoms as the main complaint, a long time from onset to admission was observed than in patients without digestive symptoms (9th 0 days versus 7th 3 days). Digestive symptoms are correlated with the outcome of the illness. Patients without digestive symptoms were discharged earlier than those who had them (60% vs 34%) [12]. Patients in intensive care were more likely to have abdominal pain and appetite loss[4], [13]. Cai J, Xu J, Lin D. observed that liver damage occurred more frequently in patients with severe illness than in patients with non-serious disease[14]. The liver function abnormalities in those with serious diseases were greater than in those with non-serious diseases[15].

Material and method.

We report the Italian health worker family case who contracted SARS-CoV-2 during working hours. The family is composed by four people (husband, wife, and two little girls). The health worker has exhibited symptoms of SARS-CoV-2 on day 1 and reconstructed the infection time about 6 days earlier. The initial symptoms were high fever, anosmia, dysgeusia, muscle aches, colds, diarrhea. He immediately practiced

home isolation, including his family members. Waiting for the oropharyngeal swab result, the breathlessness was worsened: until that time the man had taken only paracetamol and vitamin supplements. On day 4, he just received the SARS-CoV-2 confirmation of positivity and the doctor gave him immediately the therapy with hydroxychloroquine (400 mg for 8 days) and azithromycin (500mg for 8 days). The patient had some collateral effects like some symptoms on the mood tone. The wife showed symptoms of SARS-CoV-2 on the 6th day, after her husband's isolation, and she also waited 3 days before confirmation of positivity of the oropharyngeal swab result. The symptoms were the same as her husband's also she has gastrointestinal symptoms. Obtained the result of positivity to the swab test she started the therapy with Hydroxychloroquine (200 mg for 5 days) and azithromycin (500 mg for 5 days). The couple's daughters, 6 and 4 years old respectively, showed SARS-CoV-2 symptoms with a high fever and gastrointestinal tract on the tenth day after their father's isolation. They started immediately the azithromycin therapy and only on the third day the doctor performed the oropharyngeal swab. After four days the results were positive. The azithromycin was administered at the dosage based on body weight, the pediatric dosage, for only five days. Besides, they took probiotics including *Lactobacillus Reuteri* for 21 days.

Analysis.

The father had the most aggressive symptoms, making us think that the initial viral charge moment is important [16]–[18]. Despite the onset of high fever and gastrointestinal symptoms, the couple's daughters had a complete remission already during the third-day end by only antibiotic therapy administration with azithromycin. The whole family was in isolation confinement for 40 days.

Discussion.

Children with SARS-CoV-2 have the same gastrointestinal symptoms as adults. Gastrointestinal symptoms tend to become brutal [19]. Some COVID-19 patients' cadaver biopsies reported in the literature were limited to the heart, lungs, and liver inspection[20]–[22] but did not investigate other organs including the large and the small intestine. The virus dumped with feces is a potential contagious source. Although patients do not have gastrointestinal symptoms viral nucleic acids can be present in anal swab tests, from 6 to at least 14 days after the virus has turned negative in the respiratory tract. Ace receptors are found in many tissues and on many[23], [24], but a recent study has observed the RNA increase of SARS-CoV-2

through Luminex technology and proteomics MALDI-TF technique[18] in the culture of bacteria of faecal origin.

What about ACE2 receptors.

ACE2 is an 805 amino acid type I transmembrane glycoprotein and has an extracellular catalytic domain with a molecular 120kDa weight[25]. Imai et al. described that ACE2 removes a single residue from angiotensin (Ang) I to generate Ang1–9 and cleaves a single residue from Ang II to generate Ang1–7[25]. ACE2 Tissue localization is mostly in the heart (cardiomyocytes), kidneys (including the tubular epithelial cells luminal surface) testes (adult Leydig cells), and endothelium, but this enzyme is also in a wide tissues variety, like colon or lungs[25]. ACE2 receptors are present everywhere: lungs, cardiovascular system, gut, kidneys, central nervous system, and adipose tissue [26]. Therefore, the oral-fecal pathway must be considered, and the virus could be transmitted through the bathrooms and the adequate sanitation lack. This is a cause for concern about food distribution[23], [26]. A study analyses the cannabis sativa effects in intestinal epithelium tissues and shows that some cannabis lines cause an ACE2 mRNA down-regulated level. Wang, B. et al. obtained about 13 high CBD C. sativa extracts that modulate ACE2 gene expression and ACE2 protein levels. Some C. sativa lines regulate serine protease TMPRSS2, a critical protein required for the SARS-CoV2 entry into host cells[27].

What about TMPRSS2 receptors.

Recent studies have noted that TMPRSS2 inhibitors block the virus's entry [28]. The TMPRSS2 gene, human chromosome 21q22.3 [29], is about 44 kb long and includes 14 exons[30]. The entire length TMPRSS2 cDNA encodes 492amino acids polypeptide called epithelia [30]. HumanTMPRSS2 mRNA is expressed in many tissues, including, breast, bile duct, kidney, colon, small intestine, prostate, pancreas, ovary, salivary gland, stomach, and lung [30], [31]. The area where the TMPRSS2 protein and mRNA is present in the epithelial cells. In human prostate cancers, the TMPRSS2 protein is localized on the secretory epithelium apex membrane and in the lumen of the glands[31]. Many cells derived from the human prostate and colon, including APC-4, LNCaP, LoVo, T84, and Colo-205, also express mRNA TMPRSS2[32]. It activates the influenza virus by cleaving hemagglutinin, suggesting that the enzyme may contribute to the human airway virus invasion [33], [34]. TMPRSS2 Secret forms have recently been found in human seminal fluid, suggesting an adjustment. The promoter human TMPRSS2 gene responds to the 15 bp androgen in position 148 compared to the putative transcription starting site[31], [35]. TMPRSS2 upregulation by androgen appears to be mediated by the androgen

receptor[32]. Intuitively, man gender has a more level of TMPRSS2 receptors and androgen receptor no forgetting androgen hormones than woman gender.

What about RNA SARS-CoV-2 Increase load in extra body ambient.

In a recent study, Petrillo et. al observed replication of RNA SARS-CoV-2 in a vitro culture of bacteria derived from a faecal sample. They observed that at 30 days there is an 800% increasing in viral load[18]. Maybe the SARS-CoV-2 replication, in this experiment, may have happened in something exfoliated epithelium cells from the intestine, but the viral growth should not have shown an increasing trend of 800% at 30 days. Furthermore, it is now known that the exfoliated epithelium cells do not survive beyond 48 hours[36]. In the same experiment, the authors had proved the use of antibiotics to inhibit the replication of RNA SARS-CoV2 in a culture of bacteria, and they also observed metabolic major activity at biotyper test of some bacteria of Clostridium and Pseudomonas genus. The antibiotics that showed a good decrease of RNA viral load are metronidazole, amoxicillin, azithromycin, vancomycin, alone and in combination. Those who showed a worse response are clarithromycin, levofloxacin, and others [18]. In a second study, they had found some toxins like phospholipase A2 (PLA2) and others similar to conotoxins in plasma, urine, and in a culture of bacteria coming from COVID-19 patients[37].

The probable role of the PLA2.

Phospholipase A2 is important for the signal transduction process. Waite M. et al. observed that PLA2 enables leucocytes to affect some crucial responses to inflammation development[38]. Pla2 increases in acute respiratory distress syndrome[39] and depends on arachidonic acid (aa) which is low in normal conditions[40]. Arachidonic acid (aa) forms prostaglandins and thromboxane through cyclooxygenase and leukotrienes and hydroxy fatty acid through lipoxygenase[39][40]. Hydroxychloroquine and mepacrine inhibit phospholipase A2 activity and perhaps that explains their anti-inflammatory actions part[42]. Also dexamethasone inhibits it[43] [16]. While drugs that completely or mildly inhibit cyclooxygenase type 1 determine an enhancement of the lipoxygenase and thromboxane pathways.

Are useful Chloroquine (CQ) and hydroxychloroquine (HCQ)?

CQ and HCQ are aminoquinol, which have been used to treat malaria and autoimmune diseases for over 50years. Schrezenmeie et al.[44]explained that they have immunomodulatory effects. They can inhibit certain cellular functions and molecular pathways involved in immune activation by accumulating in lysosomes and phagocytic autophagosome cells and changing local pH concentrations[44].

Prevent viral fusion in the cell and are concentrated within acidic organelles such as endosomes and lysosomes. They change pH intracellular concentration. This is perhaps the mechanism in the COVID-19 treatment. Besides, studies have also revealed that these drugs interact with ACE-2 receptor glycosylation and maybe stopped the SARS-CoV-2 receptor binding[45]–[47]. Yao X. Y. e F. et al. in their study, in vitro analysis, HCQ was found to be more potent than THE QC in inhibiting SARS-CoV-2 [48], [49]. Liu J. et al., in a randomized study about 62 patients with mild COVID-19 pneumonia without hypoxia, reported that body temperature recovery time and cough remission time were significantly reduced in the HCQ treatment group. However, the study was not published in a peer-reviewed journal and there are no data about concurrent co-therapies, basic differences between groups, and blinding or placebo control lack[45]. In one study, it was associated with an undetectable SARS-CoV-2 RNA higher rate on nose-pharyngeal test for 6 days than no specific treatment[17]. Chen J et al and McCreary EK et al. established that the HCQ with azithromycin combination resulted in 100% viral clearance in 6 patients, HCQ alone resulted in a clearance of 57% [50], [51]. The same last group also published the 80 COVID-19 patients' results who received anHCQ and azithromycin combination. They noted a clinical improvement in all but one 86-year-olds who died[52]. Wange t al. e Gautret et al., studies present methodological problems [46], [53]. In these studies, although the selection is 80 people which about 50% are men and 50% women. The study has not data differences between the two sexes about therapies: HCQ only, azithromycin only, placebo; and the differences about: days and symptoms criteria binding to the choice therapies. These drugs, in some studies, have independently been shown to increase the QT interval prolongation risk, drug-induced twist points, and sudden cardiac death induced by drugs[4], [54], [55]. One study suggests that the higher CQ dosage (10-day regimen) should not be recommended for COVID-19 treatment because it has potential safety risks[45], [56], [57]. In another study in the United States, a significant variation in the QT range was noted in 84 adult patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection treated with HCQ/Azithromycin combination[48]. Finally, the National pharmacovigilance agency French has found serious cardiac events, sudden cardiac arrests, prolonged QT, arrhythmias, and syncope since the March 2020 end[49]. CQ and HCQ have also been proposed as candidates for antiviral prophylaxis against the current COVID-19 pandemic due to its proven in vitro mechanisms preventing viral fusion but the data are insufficient[52].

Conclusion.

When are matched nonspecific symptoms such as anosmia, dysgeusia, or diarrhea present in many COVID-19 patients, suggest an interest in the central neuronal pathways and especially in the autonomous nerve system [16], [37]. The nicotinic (n-aChR) and muscarinic cholinergic receptors (m1/m3) are probably affected [37].

PLA2, if present, would justify the hydroxychloroquine or dexamethasone use but the overview of the literature, which showed the data, and our observation of these four cases suggest a different time-dependent therapeutic approach. It would be important to check on a large scale the difference that could exist between the two sexes when taking hydroxychloroquine alone, azithromycin alone (or other antibiotics), both, and especially in the intake start timing, at the first or at the second or at the third day from the onset of the symptoms. Also, the use of other antibiotics like metronidazole, vancomycin, or amoxicillin at the beginning of the illness can be considered. It is certainly important to have quick and easy-to-access tests to determine if patients are suffering from SARS-CoV-2 as soon as the first symptoms appear. This can help to have a faster therapeutic choice on the management of the individual case.

The strange questions are:

- How can Azithromycin have therapeutic effects in presence of the virus and what is its correct timing use?
- How is possible that in vitro some antibiotics like metronidazole, vancomycin, azithromycin, amoxicillin can inhibit the viral load of SARS-CoV-2?
- Can the intake of cyclooxygenase 1 inhibitors drugs worsen the inflammatory aspect including pneumonia?
- It is possible the presence of a similar bacteriophage mechanism between SARS-CoV-2 and oral-faecal bacteria such as to justify the presence of gastrointestinal symptoms, anosmia, hyposmia, and the use of some antibiotics?

DECLARATIONS

The author, after the experiments carried out and published in a not review article visible in reference number 18, believes that, in the absence of control between viruses and bacteria in the last 70 years, Kock's second postulate should be updated and modified. He believes that must first be tested the new pathogens on a mixed cell line, the reason that the bacteria live on the epithelial cells, and later they can be tested in a pure cell line. Furthermore, the author believes that the Hershey and Chase method of 1952 was abandoned too soon, but it may have wider use.

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY - PATENTS & COPYRIGHTS

The use of antibiotics has been deposited as a pending patent (ITA 102020000022414) by S. Cristoni and C. Brogna. The method to use faecal samples as a source of viruses has been deposited as a pending patent (ITA 102020000022519) by C. Brogna.

References

- [1] «Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Situation Reports». <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [2] «Clinical Characteristics of Coronavirus Disease 2019 in China | NEJM». <https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2002032> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [3] «Clinical course and risk factors for mortality of adult inpatients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study - The Lancet». [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(20\)30566-3/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(20)30566-3/fulltext) (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [4] «Clinical Characteristics of 138 Hospitalized Patients With 2019 Novel Coronavirus–Infected Pneumonia in Wuhan, China | Critical Care Medicine | JAMA | JAMA Network». <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2761044> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [5] W. Zhang *et al.*, «The use of anti-inflammatory drugs in the treatment of people with severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): The Perspectives of clinical immunologists from China», *Clin. Immunol. Orlando Fla*, vol. 214, page. 108393, mag. 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.clim.2020.108393.
- [6] «Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China - PubMed». <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31986264/> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [7] «Evidence for Gastrointestinal Infection of SARS-CoV-2». <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7130181/> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [8] F. Qi, S. Qian, S. Zhang, e Z. Zhang, «Single-cell RNA sequencing of 13 human tissues identify cell types and receptors of human coronaviruses», *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, vol. 526, n. 1, page. 135–140, mag. 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.bbrc.2020.03.044.
- [9] M. L. Holshue *et al.*, «First Case of 2019 Novel Coronavirus in the United States», *N. Engl. J. Med.*, vol. 382, n. 10, page. 929–936, Mar. 2020, DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa2001191.
- [10] «Virological assessment of hospitalized patients with COVID-2019 | Nature». <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-020-2196-x> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).

- [11] X. H. Yao *et al.*, «[A pathological report of three COVID-19 cases by minimal invasive autopsies]», *Zhonghua Bing Li Xue Za Zhi*, vol. 49, n. 5, page. 411–417, mag. 2020, DOI: 10.3760/CMA.j.cn112151-20200312-00193.
- [12] L. Pan *et al.*, «Clinical Characteristics of COVID-19 Patients With Digestive Symptoms in Hubei, China: A Descriptive, Cross-Sectional, Multicenter Study», *Am. J. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 115, n. 5, page. 766–773, mag. 2020, DOI: 10.14309/Aug.0000000000000620.
- [13] «SARS-CoV-2 May Persist in Digestive Tract Longer than Respiratory Tract[v1] | Preprints». <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202002.0354/v1> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [14] C. Jiehao *et al.*, «A Case Series of Children With 2019 Novel Coronavirus Infection: Clinical and Epidemiological Features», *Clin. Infect. Dis. Off. Publ. Infect. Dis. Soc. Am.*, vol. 71, n. 6, page. 1547–1551, set. 2020, DOI: 10.1093/CID/ciaa198.
- [15] «Clinical characteristics of 82 death cases with COVID-19 | medRxiv». <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.02.26.20028191v1> (consultation feb. 04, 2021).
- [16] C. Brogna, «The Covid-19 Virus Double Pathogenic Mechanism. A New Perspective», Apr. 2020, DOI: 10.20944/preprints202004.0165.v2.
- [17] K. K.-W. To *et al.*, «Temporal profiles of viral load in posterior oropharyngeal saliva samples and serum antibody responses during infection by SARS-CoV-2: an observational cohort study», *Lancet Infect. Dis.*, vol. 20, n. 5, page. 565–574, mag. 2020, DOI: 10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30196-1.
- [18] M. Petrillo, C. Brogna, S. Cristoni, M. Querci, O. Piazza, e G. Van den Eede, «Increase of SARS-CoV-2 RNA load in faecal samples prompts for rethinking of SARS-CoV-2 biology and COVID-19 epidemiology», ott. 2020, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4088208.
- [19] R. Mao *et al.*, «Manifestations and prognosis of gastrointestinal and liver involvement in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis», *Lancet Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, vol. 5, n. 7, page. 667–678, lug. 2020, DOI: 10.1016/S2468-1253(20)30126-6.
- [20] «(24) (PDF) Liver and COVID 19 Infection: A Very Preliminary Lesson Learnt from Histological Post-mortem Findings in 48 patients». https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340937663_Liver_and_COVID_19_Infection_A_Very_Preliminary_Lesson_Learnt_from_Histological_Post-mortem_Findings_in_48_patients (consultation feb. 04, 2021).
- [21] «Pathological study of the 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) through postmortem core biopsies | Modern Pathology». <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41379-020-0536-x> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [22] S. Tian, W. Hu, L. Niu, H. Liu, H. Xu, e S.-Y. Xiao, «Pulmonary Pathology of Early-Phase 2019 Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pneumonia in Two Patients With Lung Cancer», *J. Thorac. Oncol. Off. Publ. Int. Assoc. Study Lung Cancer*, vol. 15, n. 5, page. 700–704, mag. 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.jtho.2020.02.010.
- [23] T. Santa-Coloma, «The Airborne and Gastrointestinal Coronavirus SARS-COV-2 Pathways», Apr. 2020, DOI: 10.20944/preprints202004.0133.v2.
- [24] L. Fagerberg *et al.*, «Analysis of the human tissue-specific expression by genome-wide integration of transcriptomics and antibody-based proteomics», *Mol. Cell. Proteomics MCP*, vol. 13, n. 2, page. 397–406, feb. 2014, DOI: 10.1074/MCP.M113.035600.
- [25] Y. Imai, K. Kuba, e J. M. Penninger, «Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 in acute respiratory distress syndrome», *Cell. Mol. Life Sci. CMLS*, vol. 64, n. 15, page. 2006–2012, ago. 2007, DOI: 10.1007/s00018-007-6228-6.
- [26] M. Gheblawi *et al.*, «Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2: SARS-CoV-2 Receptor and Regulator of the Renin-Angiotensin System: Celebrating the 20th Anniversary of the Discovery of ACE2», *Circ. Res.*, vol. 126, n. 10, page. 1456–1474, mag. 2020, DOI: 10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.120.317015.
- [27] B. Wang, A. Kovalchuk, D. Li, Y. Ilnytskyi, I. Kovalchuk, e O. Kovalchuk, «In Search of Preventative Strategies: Novel Anti-Inflammatory High-CBD Cannabis Sativa Extracts Modulate ACE2 Expression in COVID-19 Gateway Tissues», Apr. 2020, DOI: 10.20944/preprints202004.0315.v1.
- [28] «SARS-CoV-2 Cell Entry Depends on ACE2 and TMPRSS2 and Is Blocked by a Clinically Proven Protease Inhibitor - PubMed». <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32142651/> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).

- [29] A. Paoloni-Giacobino, H. Chen, M. C. Peitsch, C. Rossier, e S. E. Antonarakis, «Cloning of the TMPRSS2 Gene, Which Encodes a Novel Serine Protease with Transmembrane, LDLRA, and SRCR Domains and Maps to 21q22.3», *Genomics*, vol. 44, n. 3, page. 309–320, set. 1997, DOI: 10.1006/geno.1997.4845.
- [30] E. Jacquinet, N. V. Rao, G. V. Rao, e J. R. Hoidal, «Cloning, genomic organization, chromosomal assignment and expression of a novel mosaic serine proteinase: epitheliasin», *FEBS Lett.*, pg. 8, 2000.
- [31] B. Lin *et al.*, «Prostate-localized and androgen-regulated expression of the membrane-bound serine protease TMPRSS2», *Cancer Res.*, vol. 59, n. 17, page. 4180–4184, set. 1999.
- [32] D. E. Afar *et al.*, «Catalytic cleavage of the androgen-regulated TMPRSS2 protease results in its secretion by prostate and prostate cancer epithelia», *Cancer Res.*, vol. 61, n. 4, page. 1686–1692, Feb. 2001.
- [33] E. Böttcher-Friebertshäuser *et al.*, «Cleavage of influenza virus hemagglutinin by airway proteases TMPRSS2 and HAT differs in subcellular localization and susceptibility to protease inhibitors», *J. Virol.*, vol. 84, n. 11, page. 5605–5614, Jun. 2010, DOI: 10.1128/JVI.00140-10.
- [34] «Proteolytic Activation of Influenza Viruses by Serine Proteases TMPRSS2 and HAT from Human Airway Epithelium | Journal of Virology». <https://jvi.asm.org/content/80/19/9896> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [35] Y.-W. Chen *et al.*, «TMPRSS2, a serine protease expressed in the prostate on the apical surface of luminal epithelial cells and released into semen in prostasomes, is misregulated in prostate cancer cells», *Am. J. Pathol.*, vol. 176, n. 6, page. 2986–2996, Jun. 2010, DOI: 10.2353/ajpath.2010.090665.
- [36] B. Kaeffer, «Survival of Exfoliated Epithelial Cells: A Delicate Balance between Anoikis and Apoptosis», *Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology*, ott. 27, 2011. <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/bmri/2011/534139/> (consultation feb. 13, 2021).
- [37] C. Brogna, M. Petrillo, S. Cristoni, M. Querci, O. Piazza, e G. Van den Eede, «Detection of toxin-like peptides in plasma and urine samples from COVID-19 patients», ott. 2020, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4139341.
- [38] «Biochemistry of lipids and membranes: Edited by D E Vance and J E Vance. pp 593. Benjamin/Cummings, California. 1985 ISBN 0-8053-9420-6 - Vella - 1986 - Biochemical Education - Wiley Online Library». [https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1016/0307-4412\(86\)90032-4](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1016/0307-4412(86)90032-4) (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [39] P. Vadas e W. Pruzanski, «Role of secretory phospholipases A2 in the pathobiology of disease», *Lab. Invest. J. Tech. Methods Pathol.*, vol. 55, n. 4, page. 391–404, ott. 1986.
- [40] M. Hamberg e B. Samuelsson, «Prostaglandin endoperoxides. Novel transformations of arachidonic acid in human platelets», *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, vol. 71, n. 9, page. 3400–3404, set. 1974, DOI: 10.1073/pnas.71.9.3400.
- [41] M. Hamberg e B. Samuelsson, «On the mechanism of the biosynthesis of prostaglandins E-1 and F-1-alpha», *J. Biol. Chem.*, vol. 242, n. 22, page. 5336–5343, Nov. 1967.
- [42] S. D'Alessandro *et al.*, «The Use of Antimalarial Drugs against Viral Infection», *Microorganisms*, vol. 8, n. 1, gen. 2020, DOI: 10.3390/microorganisms8010085.
- [43] J. D. Croxtall, Q. Choudhury, e R. J. Flower, «Glucocorticoids act within minutes to inhibit recruitment of signaling factors to activated EGF receptors through a receptor-dependent, transcription-independent mechanism», *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, vol. 130, n. 2, page. 289–298, mag. 2000, DOI: 10.1038/SJ.bjp.0703272.
- [44] E. Schrezenmeier e T. Dörner, «Mechanisms of action of hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine: implications for rheumatology», *Nat. Rev. Rheumatol.*, vol. 16, n. 3, pagg. 155–166, mar. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41584-020-0372-x.
- [45] J. Liu *et al.*, «Hydroxychloroquine, a less toxic derivative of chloroquine, is effective in inhibiting SARS-CoV-2 infection in vitro», *Cell Discov.*, vol. 6, page. 16, 2020, DOI: 10.1038/s41421-020-0156-0.
- [46] M. Wang *et al.*, «Remdesivir and chloroquine effectively inhibit the recently emerged novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) in vitro», *Cell Res.*, vol. 30, n. 3, page. 269–271, Mar. 2020, DOI: 10.1038/s41422-020-0282-0.
- [47] C.-C. Lu, M.-Y. Chen, e Y.-L. Chang, «Potential therapeutic agents against COVID-19: What we know so far», *J. Chin. Med. Assoc.*, Apr. 2020, DOI: 10.1097/JCMA.0000000000000318.

- [48] X. Yao *et al.*, «In Vitro Antiviral Activity and Projection of Optimized Dosing Design of Hydroxychloroquine for the Treatment of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)», *Clin. Infect. Dis. Off. Publ. Infect. Dis. Soc. Am.*, vol. 71, n. 15, page. 732–739, lug. 2020, DOI: 10.1093/CID/ciaa237.
- [49] « Review of Emerging Pharmacotherapy for the Treatment of Coronavirus Disease 2019 - Barlow - 2020 - Pharmacotherapy: The Journal of Human Pharmacology and Drug Therapy - Wiley Online Library». <https://accpjournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/phar.2398> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [50] J. Chen *et al.*, « [A pilot study of hydroxychloroquine in treatment of patients with moderate COVID-19]», *Zhejiang Xue Xue Bao Yi Xue Ban J. Zhejiang Univ. Med. Sci.*, vol. 49, n. 2, page. 215–219, mag. 2020, DOI : 10.3785/j.issn.1008-9292.2020.03.03.
- [51] « Coronavirus Disease 2019 Treatment: A Review of Early and Emerging Options | Open Forum Infectious Diseases | Oxford Academic». <https://academic.oup.com/ofid/article/7/4/ofaa105/5811022> (consultation Feb. 04, 2021).
- [52] P. Gautret *et al.*, «Hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin as a treatment of COVID-19: results of an open-label non-randomized clinical trial», *Int. J. Antimicrob. Agents*, vol. 56, n. 1, page. 105949, lug. 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2020.105949.
- [53] P. Gautret *et al.*, «Clinical and microbiological effect of a combination of hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin in 80 COVID-19 patients with at least a six-day follow up: A pilot observational study», *Travel Med. Infect. Dis.*, vol. 34, page. 101663, 2020, DOI : 10.1016/j.tmaid.2020.101663.
- [54] Y. Yan *et al.*, « Anti-malaria drug chloroquine is highly effective in treating avian influenza A H5N1 virus infection in an animal model», *Cell Res.*, vol. 23, n. 2, page. 300–302, Feb. 2013, DOI: 10.1038/cr.2012.165.
- [55] S. A. B. Jr, C. A. M. G, e C. R., «Effects of chloroquine on viral infections: an old drug against today's diseases?», *Lancet Infect. Dis.*, vol. 3, n. 11, page. 722–727, nov. 2003, DOI: 10.1016/s1473-3099(03)00806-5.
- [56] C.-Y. Chen, F.-L. Wang, e C.-C. Lin, «Chronic hydroxychloroquine use associated with QT prolongation and refractory ventricular arrhythmia», *Clin. Toxicol. Phila. Pa*, vol. 44, n. 2, page. 173–175, 2006, DOI: 10.1080/15563650500514558.
- [57] A. Kezerashvili, H. Khattak, A. Barsky, R. Nazari, e J. D. Fisher, «Azithromycin as a cause of QT-interval prolongation and torsade de points in the absence of other known precipitating factors», *J. Interv. Card. Electrophysiol. Int. J. Arrhythm. Pacing*, vol. 18, n. 3, page. 243–246, apr. 2007, DOI: 10.1007/s10840-007-9124-y.